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Learning or popularity: How does R&D network formation and innovative performance interact with each other? A SAOM approach¹

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Introduction

Ever since Powell (1996) pointed to the R&D network as a locus for industrial innovation, the effect that a firm's position in such a network has on its innovative performance has been a subject of study and debate in the innovation literature. While a link between network position and innovation has been properly established, the endogenous interaction between the two variables has gone underexplored. Whereas the previous literature on R&D networks' effect on innovation have been based on “flattening” network parameters to a format that is amenable to traditional statistical analysis, the ambition of this paper is to use a modelling approach that retains the richness of the network data in order to more properly explore the endogenous interaction between innovative activity and network ties. To do this, I exploit a particularly rich data set of R&D collaborators, and estimate a Stochastic Actor-Oriented Model (SAOM) using the SIENA modelling software developed by Snijders and Stieglich (2010). The goal is to create a model that measures the endogenous processes between innovation performance and network formation, and use this to simulate higher and lower rates of network formation in order to measure network impact.

Background

The role of R&D networks in innovation

Inter-organisational collaborations is increasingly positioned at the core of innovation policy. To boost the creation, spread and application of new technologies and scientific knowledge, governments use R&D funds to incentivise firms to form collaborative ties with other firms, as well as knowledge-based organisations such as universities and research institutes. These ties form growing collaboration networks, which have profound effects on how knowledge is created and diffused among different firms and research organisations. This linking of potentially heterogenous pools of knowledge is seen as a source of “recombinatory potential” (Nelson, 1982), and so the determinants of network formation and the network's effect on firms' innovation performance have long been of interest to the innovation literature.

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The correlation between being centrally embedded in a research network and being innovative has been relatively well established (e.g. Ahuja, 2000, Baum et al., 2000, Schilling and Phelps, 2007, Liang and Liu, 2018) (For a systematic review of this literature, see Wang et al., 2015). In particular, the degree centrality – i.e. the measure describing the number of a firm’s collaboration partners – is seen to be positively linked to innovative performance. Other measures, such as eigenvector centrality (having ties to firms that are themselves well-connected) and betweenness (being embedded in such a way that you connect otherwise disjointed regions of the network) have been shown to have similar connections to firms’ innovation output.

Shortcomings of the extant literature

In their paper ‘Dynamic networks and behaviour: Separating selection from influence’ (2010), Steglich et al. argue that many commonly used approaches measuring the relationship between network formation and node behaviour are insufficient or overly limited. According to them, this relationship has primarily been studied in two ways: (1) basing analysis of node behaviour solely on dyadic relationships, and/or (2) “flattening” the network data by extracting centrality measures for each node, and then using these as variables for a traditional regression analysis the units. The latter of these dominates the literature on R&D network position effects.

According to Steglich et al. (2010), flattening network data into traditional data sets robs networks of vital information of how networks form, and how you can analyse the association between network formation and node behaviour and characteristics. For one, the nature of network data breaks with the fundamental independence assumption of traditional regression analysis. Furthermore, there are known dynamics inherent to network structures that can be used to predict network formation, such as triadic closure. If you erase these structures from the data by flattening it, the presence or absence of network links can mistakenly be attributed to individual node characteristics or behaviour.

Steglich et al. contend that while these shortcomings do not necessarily invalidate studies based flattened network data, it is a major problem that most studies do not even acknowledge or discuss these shortcomings. It is my view that this contention holds true for the extant literature on R&D networks and innovation, and no paper using this flattening method seem to go into depth in discussing this shortcoming. This is of concern, as there is an immediately intuitive logic to hypothesise that there is an endogenous relationship between a firm’s innovation performance and its position in a collaboration network. In short: Do firms become more innovative by being central in the network, or do more innovative firms attract more collaborators and make them more central? The immediately intuitive answer must naturally be “both”: There is a co-evolution between a firm’s R&D network centrality and its innovative capabilities. An innovative firm may tend to become central in an R&D network because, as they started innovating, they became a more interesting collaboration partner for other firms (“selection”). At the same time, it might be that the connection to partners facilitated the firm’s increased innovation in the first place (“influence”). Crucially, which of the two patterns plays a stronger role can be decisive for success or failure of R&D policies meant to boost innovation.

Methods and data

In order to model the interaction of network positioning and innovation, I intend to use the SIENA modelling framework (Snijders et al., 2010). SIENA is a form of Stochastic Actor Oriented Modelling (SOAM) specifically designed to handle longitudinal network data, together with a set of both constant and dynamic individual variables at the node level.

SIENA is a relatively popular tool in the R&D network literature, but its use has been limited to model the determinants of network formation, and so far not been brought to bear on the question of how networks affect innovation output.

In order to achieve this, I mean to employ a dataset obtained from the Norwegian Research Council (RCN) detailing all publicly funded and/or tax deducted R&D projects in Norway in the period 2008-2018. In addition to having near-full coverage of formalised R&D collaboration in this 10 year period, the data set is also connected to Norwegian registry data detailing a wide variety of input factors (such as firm size, turnover, employees, sectors etc.), databases of intellectual property rights registries, such as patenting and trademark applications, as well as questionnaire data on firm-level R&D efforts from three waves of the Norwegian Community Innovation Survey (CIS). While many sectors are available for future study, I am looking at a subset cluster of industrial manufacturers who are not only R&D active, but have a relatively high propensity to use the patenting and trademarking systems.

While the modelling work is still in progress, the hope is that this rare wealth of R&D network data with accompanying metadata will make possible analysis that have previously been difficult to perform.

References

Balland, P.-A., 2012. Proximity and the Evolution of Collaboration Networks: Evidence from Research and Development Projects within the Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) Industry. *Reg. Stud.* 46, 741–756. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00343404.2010.529121>

Nelson, R.R. (Richard R., 1982. *An evolutionary theory of economic change* / Richard R. Nelson and Sidney G. Winter. Belknap Press of Harvard University Press, Cambridge, Mass.

Snijders, T.A.B., van de Bunt, G.G., Steglich, C.E.G., 2010. Introduction to stochastic actor-based models for network dynamics. *Soc. Netw.* 32, 44–60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socnet.2009.02.004>

Steglich, C., Snijders, T.A.B., Pearson, M., 2010. 8. Dynamic Networks and Behavior: Separating Selection from Influence. *Sociol. Methodol.* 40, 329–393. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9531.2010.01225.x>

Wang, H., Zhao, J., Li, Y., Li, C., 2015. Network centrality, organizational innovation, and performance: A meta-analysis. *Can. J. Adm. Sci. Can. Sci. Adm.* 32, 146–159.